

Appendix from ASTRODEEP-JWST: NIRC*am*-HST multiband photometry and redshifts for half a million sources in six extragalactic deep fields

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ABSTRACT

This document provides the Appendix Section from the paper “ASTRODEEP-JWST: NIRC*am*-HST multiband photometry and redshifts for half a million sources in six extragalactic deep fields” by E. Merlin et al., 2024, DOI 10.1051/0004-6361/202451409.

The catalogues are available for download from the ASTRODEEP website <https://astrodeep.eu/astrodeep-jwst-catalogs/>. Updates and/or additional releases will be documented on the website.

It is also possible to visualize and explore the catalogues on the Cosmological Surveys Rainbow Database, http://arcoirix.cab.inta-csic.es/Rainbow_navigator_public/ (Pérez-González et al. 2005, 2008; Barro et al. 2019).

The “optimal” photometric catalogues (see Sect. 3.4 of the main paper) and the photo-*z* catalogues (see Section 5) for all fields are also available in electronic form at the CDS via anonymous ftp to cdsarc.u-strasbg.fr (130.79.128.5) or via <http://cdsweb.u-strasbg.fr/cgi-bin/qcat?J/A+A/>.

1 Appendix A: Catalogue format

2 We release several catalogues for each field, among which one
 3 (named “optap”-catalogue) is obtained assigning to each source
 4 the colours computed in its “optimal” aperture (see Section
 5 3.4). The catalogues are published in fits format, and come
 6 with a README file that explains the meaning and format of
 7 the columns. All catalogues first list a set of columns indicat-
 8 ing the unique identifiers of the detected objects, their position
 9 in equatorial coordinates and in pixels, and some values from
 10 the SExtractor detection run on the F356W+F444W stack mo-
 11 saics: ISOAREA_IMAGE, CLASS_STAR, FLAGS, FLUX_RADIUS,
 12 FLUX_AUTO, FLUXERR_AUTO. Then, some measures obtained
 13 with A-PHOT again on the detection stack are listed: the major
 14 semi-axis of the elliptical isophote, the ellipticity and the posi-
 15 tion angle, and the Kron radius (in pixels). The total fluxes in the
 16 16 photometric bands, computed as described in Section 3.5, are
 17 then given, followed by the corresponding 16 uncertainties (all
 18 in μJy units). Finally, the last column lists the flags discussed in
 19 Section 3.5. In the “optap”-catalogue, the value of the “optimal”
 20 aperture is also given (in arcseconds). We also release the origi-
 21 nal raw catalogue containing all the measured aperture fluxes.

22 We separately release a set of photometric redshift cata-
 23 logues estimated from the “optap”-catalogue with local back-
 24 ground subtraction. For each source we list the ID, RA and Dec,
 25 the spectroscopic redshift when available, the four estimates of
 26 the photometric redshift (see Section 5), and the flag assigned
 27 to the source as reported also in the “optap”-catalogue, with the
 28 additional indication of a negative sign for the sources lacking
 29 information in the bands necessary to identify the Lyman break.

30 Appendix B: Astrometry

31 As explained in Section 3.1, we re-aligned HST mosaics to the
 32 NIRCcam grid by means of an automatic procedure. Table B.1
 33 lists the offsets in RA and Dec after the procedure, for all the
 34 bands and fields. We point out that the CANDELS EGS and
 35 CEERS HDR1 HST data are obtained from the same observa-
 36 tions, but the latter has been re-aligned to Gaia-DR3; since we
 37 took care to correct all of the images for astrometric accuracy,
 38 the two datasets should be perfectly consistent.

Table B.1: The median and MAD of the astrometric offsets of the HST bands.

Band	N_{obj}	ΔRA (")	ΔDEC (")
ABELL2744			
F435W	1307	0.009 ± 0.02	0.000 ± 0.01
F606W	3309	0.001 ± 0.02	0.001 ± 0.01
F814W	3188	-0.001 ± 0.02	-0.001 ± 0.01
F105W	4595	0.003 ± 0.01	0.001 ± 0.01
F125W	2170	0.003 ± 0.02	-0.001 ± 0.01
F140W	849	0.005 ± 0.02	0.003 ± 0.01
F160W	2054	0.003 ± 0.02	0.000 ± 0.01
CEERS			
F606W	7063	0.044 ± 0.03	0.032 ± 0.02
F814W	8615	0.066 ± 0.02	0.041 ± 0.01
F105W	1437	0.007 ± 0.05	0.010 ± 0.03
F125W	8470	0.027 ± 0.01	0.036 ± 0.01
F160W	4355	0.064 ± 0.05	0.040 ± 0.02
JADES-GN			
F435W	1144	0.036 ± 0.05	0.015 ± 0.02
F606W	1822	0.045 ± 0.04	0.015 ± 0.02
F814W	3228	0.040 ± 0.03	0.015 ± 0.01
F105W	2800	0.041 ± 0.02	0.012 ± 0.01
F125W	3430	0.039 ± 0.01	0.013 ± 0.00
F140W	1532	0.044 ± 0.01	0.015 ± 0.01
F160W	1436	0.041 ± 0.04	0.013 ± 0.02
JADES-GS			
F435W	13997	0.006 ± 0.03	-0.015 ± 0.03
F606W	21408	0.004 ± 0.02	-0.012 ± 0.02
F814W	19677	0.000 ± 0.02	-0.010 ± 0.01
F105W	12169	0.005 ± 0.01	-0.013 ± 0.01
F125W	18764	0.007 ± 0.01	-0.013 ± 0.01
F140W	8542	0.008 ± 0.01	-0.014 ± 0.01
F160W	6235	0.006 ± 0.03	-0.013 ± 0.02
NGDEEP			
F435W	758	0.082 ± 0.04	-0.058 ± 0.03
F606W	1194	0.077 ± 0.03	-0.052 ± 0.03
F775W	1121	0.077 ± 0.03	-0.052 ± 0.03
F814W	1096	0.079 ± 0.03	-0.053 ± 0.02
F105W	815	0.091 ± 0.01	-0.049 ± 0.01
F125W	965	0.091 ± 0.01	-0.050 ± 0.01
F160W	506	0.089 ± 0.02	-0.049 ± 0.02
PRIMER-COSMOS			
F435W	733	0.010 ± 0.04	0.012 ± 0.05
F606W	1279	-0.011 ± 0.03	-0.022 ± 0.03
F814W	2925	-0.004 ± 0.01	-0.008 ± 0.01
F125W	4704	-0.004 ± 0.01	-0.011 ± 0.01
F140W	2797	-0.006 ± 0.01	-0.006 ± 0.02
F160W	3709	-0.005 ± 0.02	-0.011 ± 0.02
PRIMER-UDS			
F435W	1214	0.008 ± 0.04	0.000 ± 0.04
F606W	3613	-0.003 ± 0.03	0.010 ± 0.03
F814W	4779	-0.003 ± 0.03	0.009 ± 0.03
F125W	3911	0.010 ± 0.01	-0.004 ± 0.01
F140W	1653	0.010 ± 0.02	-0.004 ± 0.02
F160W	4915	0.010 ± 0.03	-0.005 ± 0.04

Notes. The values are computed by cross-matching N_{obj} sources and corrected before re-projecting the HST images to the JWST grid. For each field, the F160W values are the coordinate offsets between the original HST F160W and the NIRCcam F150W band, while the others refer to the offsets between the given band and F160W band after it was re-aligned to the F150W.

Appendix C: Selection of point-like and potentially spurious sources

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The PCA technique described in Section 3.5 works as follows. We fed the `scikit-learn` module `decomposition.PCA` with three parameters from the `SEXTRACTOR` detection catalogue, i.e. the signal-to-noise ratio S/N obtained as the ratio between `FLUX_AUTO` and `FLUXERR_AUTO`, the peak surface brightness above background `MUMAX`, and the half light radius `FLUX_RADIUS`. We used a sub-sample of the `PRIMER-COSMOS` `SEXTRACTOR` detection catalogue to determine the principal components matrix $[[0.38283975$ 0.65126842 0.65519704], [0.92363354 -0.28388812 -0.25750461]] (with explained variance ratio [0.65961785 0.27738227]), and then applied this matrix to the full catalogues of all fields. The loci of PLS and PSS are easily identified in the resulting principal components diagram, and after a rigid anti-clockwise rotation of 66.5° PSS can be singled out by a simple law, $0.15 < \text{rPCA2} < 0$ & $\text{rPCA2} < c_{st}$ (where $\text{rPCA}i$ indicates the value of the rotated component). PSS can be identified as those in the uppermost region of the diagram, using the law $\text{rPC2} > c_{sp1} \times \log_{10}(1 + \text{rPC1}) + c_{sp2}$ & $\text{rPC1} > c_{sp3}$. The exact definition of the locus of the two populations slightly varies from field to field, as shown by the values of the constants reported in Table C.1.

We point out that this approach joins two similar and complementary techniques using diagnostic diagrams to identify the loci occupied by point-like and spurious sources, i.e. the S/N vs radius plane and the μ -mag vs mag plane. Fig. C.1 shows the PCA plane for all fields in the left column, and the two diagrams corresponding to the other techniques in the central and right columns.

Table C.1: Constants used to single out stars and potentially spurious objects in the rotated PCA plane.

Field	c_{st}	c_{sp1}	c_{sp2}	c_{sp3}
ABELL2744	0.5	0	1.75	-0.2
CEERS	0.5	3	2	-10
JADES-GN	0.8	3	2	-10
JADES-GS	0.5	5	2.5	-10
NGDEEP	0.8	3	2	-10
PRIMER-COSMOS	0.5	0	2.2	-0.2
PRIMER-UDS	0.5	0	2	-10

Fig. C.1: Star/galaxy separation and flagging of spurious sources. From left to right: as obtained in the PCA plane described in Section 3.5, projected on the hlr vs. S/N plane, projected on the μ_{MAX} - MAG vs. MAG plane. The last column shows the values of the FWHM in the detection F356W+F444W stack, for the sources identified as point-source.

Appendix D: Comparisons with other photometric catalogues

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Fig. D.1 to D.6 show how the photometry obtained in this work compares to that from other available catalogues. For each field we consider recent NIRCcam-based catalogues and archival HST based data, from CANDELS or ASTRODEEP. For the latter, we used the K_s and IRAC CH1-2 bands as proxies for the F200W, F356W and F444W JWST bands, applying the following colour corrections, based on Bruzual & Charlot (2003) theoretical templates: $K_s = F200W - 0.06$, $IRAC1 = F356W + 0.02$, $IRAC2 = F444W - 0.01$.

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Each panel of the plots shows the comparison for one colour, with the relative difference $\Delta c/c$ (i.e. colour measured in this work minus colour in the reference work, divided by colour in the archival work) as a function of the magnitude of the second band in this work (e.g., F444W magnitude if the colour is F356W-F444W). The blue line is the median of the distribution. We consider sources with $S/N > 5$ and $flag < 200$. See Section 4 for more details.

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Fig. D.1: Comparison of colours measured in this work and archival catalogues. Shown are relative errors Δc , i.e. the colours measured in this work minus those in the reference catalogues), vs. the second band magnitude in this work catalogue (e.g. F444W for the F356-F444W colour). Top to bottom: ABELL2744 vs. P23 and NGDEEP vs. Finkelstein’s catalogue (priv. comm.). The number of cross-matched sources after excluding those with $S/N < 5$ in any of the two catalogues or $\text{flag} \geq 200$ in this work is also given in each panel; the blue line is the median of the distribution.

Fig. D.2: Same as Fig. D.1, for (top to bottom) ABELL2744 vs. Weaver et al. (2024) and CEERS vs. Finkelstein et al. (2023).

Fig. D.3: Same as Fig. D.1, for JADES-GN and JADES-GS vs. the JADES team catalogues (Rieke et al. 2023).

Fig. D.4: Same as Fig. D.1, for ABELL2744 vs. Merlin et al. (2016) showing individual points rather than a density hexbin plot because of the small number of cross-matched sources, and PRIMER-COSMOS vs. Nayyeri et al. (2017). The HST colours are transformed into JWST colours by means of the corrections described in Appendix D.

PRIMER-UDS: this work vs. CANDELS (matched tot.: 28222)

CEERS: this work vs. CANDELS (matched tot.: 20013)

Fig. D.5: Same as Fig. D.1, for PRIMER-UDS vs. Galametz et al. (2013), and CEERS vs. Stefanon et al. (2017).

Fig. D.6: Same as Fig. D.1, JADES-GS vs. Merlin et al. (2021) and NGDEEP vs. Merlin et al. (2021), the latter showing individual points rather than a density hexbin plot because of the small number of cross-matched sources. The HST colours are transformed into JWST colours by means of the corrections described in Appendix D.

62 **Appendix E: Photometric redshift validation**

63 In Fig. E.1 we show the comparison between the spectroscopic and photometric redshifts, the latter computed as the median of the
 64 three runs with (i) ZPHOT, (ii) EAzy with eazy_v1.3, and (iii) EAzy with Larson et al. (2023) FSPS Set 1 + Set 4 templates, as
 65 described in Section 5. Table E.1 summarises the statistics for all four runs.

Table E.1: Comparative statistics for photometric vs. spectroscopic redshifts.

	N	100×mean	100×stdev	100×median	100×NMAD	η
ABELL2744						
ZPHOT	1355	0.57	4.28	0.47	3.33	10.04
EAzy v1.3	1354	-0.81	4.31	-0.46	3.36	13.81
EAzy Larson Lya	1338	-0.15	4.64	-0.28	3.29	13.75
EAzy Larson LyaRed	1338	-0.32	4.70	-0.33	3.46	14.28
CEERS						
ZPHOT	3186	1.17	4.63	0.89	3.64	7.97
EAzy v1.3	3182	0.38	4.55	0.41	3.59	7.54
EAzy Larson Lya	3180	-0.40	4.96	-0.26	4.04	9.03
EAzy Larson LyaRed	3180	-0.41	4.97	-0.30	4.08	9.18
JADES-GN						
ZPHOT	1848	0.81	4.25	0.75	3.47	6.71
EAzy v1.3	1846	-0.24	4.30	0.01	2.98	8.88
EAzy Larson Lya	1841	-0.74	4.08	-0.53	2.89	8.53
EAzy Larson LyaRed	1841	-0.77	4.10	-0.55	2.93	8.75
JADES-GS						
ZPHOT	2021	0.41	4.01	0.32	3.02	5.79
EAzy v1.3	2019	-0.57	4.05	-0.35	2.91	10.10
EAzy Larson Lya	2017	-0.75	3.80	-0.47	2.81	9.92
EAzy Larson LyaRed	2017	-0.85	3.83	-0.54	2.84	10.21
NGDEEP						
ZPHOT	128	1.46	4.08	0.92	3.10	10.16
EAzy v1.3	128	-0.10	4.26	0.21	3.62	9.38
EAzy Larson Lya	128	-0.29	4.16	-0.14	3.76	15.62
EAzy Larson LyaRed	128	-0.29	4.18	-0.10	3.80	16.41
PRIMER-COSMOS						
ZPHOT	4413	1.37	4.61	1.32	4.15	6.80
EAzy v1.3	4408	-0.03	4.59	0.10	3.64	7.17
EAzy Larson Lya	4399	-0.63	4.69	-0.36	3.85	8.98
EAzy Larson LyaRed	4399	-0.65	4.71	-0.37	3.89	9.09
PRIMER-UDS						
ZPHOT	3721	1.03	4.50	0.95	3.80	5.80
EAzy v1.3	3719	-0.05	4.55	0.09	3.65	5.22
EAzy Larson Lya	3713	-0.64	4.86	-0.43	3.85	7.41
EAzy Larson LyaRed	3713	-0.65	4.86	-0.46	3.87	7.57

Notes. The listed values are: number N of matched sources (the number can vary due to failings in the fitting procedures of the different codes); mean, standard deviation, median and NMAD of the quantity $|z_{phot} - z_{spec}|/(1 + z_{spec})$, all multiplied by 100 to make the differences clearer; and percentage of outliers $f_{outliers}$ as described in Section 5, for each run using different software and/or templates, and for each field.

Fig. E.1: Accuracy of photometric redshifts (median of the three runs described in Section 5) on spectroscopic samples, for all fields together (top left panel), and separately for each field. In each panel, N is the number of sources; $f_{outliers}$ is the percentage of sources with $|z_{phot} - z_{spec}| / (1 + z_{spec}) > 0.15$; the other statistics are computed on non-outliers, with $NMAD = 1.48 \times \text{median}[|z_{phot} - z_{spec}| / (1 + z_{spec})]$. colour coding is $\langle S/N \rangle = (S/N_{F444W} + S/N_{F356W} + S/N_{F277W} + S/N_{F200W}) / 4$.

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